

TEACHING LANGUAGES BY EFFECTIVELY USEAGE OF IMITATION

Dushatova Shohsanam Baxtiyor qizi

Fergana State University, EFL teacher, sh.dushatova@pf.fdu.uz

Esajonova Feruzaxon G'ulomjon qizi

Fergana State University, 3rd year student

Abstract: As we are living in the developed era, learning a foreign language is becoming one of the most indispensable capability. The relevance of using games in the methodology of teaching foreign languages is related to the complexity and versatility of the problem. In this article, the importance of role playing in learning is highlighted.

Key words and phrases: Imitation, foreign language, learning, methods, strengthening, exercises, games, technique, speech, situation.

Learning a foreign language is considered as one of the most important faculty in human society today. Language, which is a means of communication, can be acquired in a natural environment, for example in the family, among the public, or in a lesson. Many parents put an effort to teach their child a foreign language from a young age. Well, if the parent himself can speak a foreign language fluently, then he will have the opportunity to teach the child a foreign language without spending extra money on special courses. For instance, speaking English or listening to music in that language. But what about parents who do not know a foreign language?

A new stage, a new era has begun in the teaching of foreign languages in our country. In the course of foreign language lessons, advanced pedagogical technologies, interactive, innovative methods, communicative and informational methods are being demanded to use. According to it, textbooks were created for students of general education schools and vocational colleges. Foreign language learning is divided into four skills (reading, speaking, listening and speaking), and separate concepts and skills are given for each of them [7, 170].

Language learning is a time-consuming and laborious process, whether it occurs in an authentic or an organized context. Children usually acquire their first language from 2 to 5 ages to achieve full grammatical competence, during which time they are exposed to massive amounts of input. The same is undoubtedly true of second language acquisition. If learners do not receive exposure to the target language, they cannot acquire it [10, 64]

Many scientists say that you should start teaching a foreign language before the age of 3. According to recent studies, 70-80% of the development of brain cells is loaded at this age. If so, your future genius knows three languages. The relevance of using games in the methodology of teaching foreign languages is associated with the complexity and versatility of the problem under consideration.

The usage of various teaching methods assists to consolidate language phenomena in memory, create more stable visual and auditory images, and keep students interested and active. Games which are played through imitation, creates a wide range of chances to improve the educational process. The action game is regarded as a methodological technique belonging to the group of active methods of teaching practical knowledge in a foreign language. The teaching method has been moving to action games for a long time. Learning through action games mainly speech, game and educational activity can be of benefit.

Action games can be included in educational settings, because it largely determines the choice of language tools, helps to develop speech skills and abilities. It allows to imitate students' communication in different speech situations.

Playing the role of another person in imitation games is an important helper in learning a foreign language. Through imitation, the child remembers words and dialogues well.

F. Guen's method of learning a foreign language: Among the representatives of the natural method, the French methodologist Guen advocated learning a foreign language practically as if he were learning his mother tongue. He was the first in

methodology to discover the classification of the lexicon by topics (life at home, school, society, nature) [6, 34].

He proposed the following rules for learning a foreign language:

1. A person learns a language based on his needs.
2. The teaching unit is chosen not by language, but by words.
3. Oral speech is considered primary in language teaching.

F. Guen, like M. Berlins, uses such conditions as demonstrativeness, not relying on the mother tongue, and the dependence of grammar on the lexicon.

In short, it is easier to learn a foreign language through imitation and action games. Nowadays, the vast majority of people are utilizing imitation in purpose of learning foreign languages around the world. Apart from that, organizing a foreign language highly depends on the students themselves rather than the training centers and teachers. In addition, the rightly chosen methodology like the one above, confidence and passion are enough to acquire a foreign language.

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